

Genetic Indicators for Nature Monitoring - GINAMO

**Report title: GINAMO full data management plan -
v1**

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Report short title: Ginamo data
management plan - v1
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 Ginamo data management plan - v1
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Document history

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30/07/2024	version1	M. Heuertz	INRAE		Version submitted to Biodiversa+ on 30/07/2024
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Content

"Genetic Indicators for NAture Monitoring" DMP

Plan de gestion de données créé à l'aide de DMP OPIDoR, basé sur le modèle "Science Europe: structured template" fourni par Science Europe.

Plan Details

Plan title "Genetic Indicators for NAture Monitoring" DMP

Deliverable D1.2

Version First version

Plan purpose/scope **Work package structure**

- **WP1 : Coordination and management** (Lead: Christina Hvilsom) is designed to coordinate, oversee and manage GINAMO consortium activities, including GINAMOs consortium communication internally and externally, liaising with relevant higher level stakeholder initiatives and interconnecting data outputs from WP5-6
 - **D1.1 - Task T1.1** implement a recruitment strategy for PhD students, postdocs and scientists, ensure equal opportunities and foster research collaboration through knowledge transfer, training and researcher mobility for internships or exchanges, and involvement in scientific publications. GINAMO will adhere to FAIR principles for data management and data retrieval, following the European Strategy for data.
 - **D1.2 - Task T1.2 Conceive GINAMO's data management plan** - full data management plan for GINAMO, integrating and including management of WP5 data (simulated genetic data, reused genetic and proxy data, and newly generated code) and the survey and data from WP6 on social sciences. GINAMO activities centre around co-creation, feeding into (T1.3)
 - **D1.3 - Task T1.3 GINAMO internal and external higher level communication** - produce relevant and impactful internal consortium and external higher level stakeholder communication and interaction, such as with the European Commission, GEO BON, Natura 2000, EUFORGEN, and EuropaBON to harmonise and link ongoing initiatives. Guidance documents and educational materials produced by WP2-6 will be harmonised and coherence towards stakeholders ensured. The project coordinator, assisted by a steering committee composed of the PIs of each partner, will overview all progress regarding milestones, deliverables, and impact, which will be on the agenda of the biannual steering committee meetings and general assemblies. Monthly progress check-ins will be held with all WP leaders and all current governing, strategic and operational documents will be collated in a shared online folder, accessible to the entire consortium team, including for efficient Risk management.
- **WP2 : Best practices for assessing Ne from genetic data** (Lead: Pauline Garnier-Géré and Joost Raeymaekers) will address the major factors that affect contemporary Ne and its estimates,

including different spatial distributions (e.g. from small to very large geographic scales, from continuous to subdivided populations with variable migration rates, life history traits (e.g., longevity, variance in reproductive success), genetic marker number and types (e.g. genome-wide nucleotide variants, microsatellites), sampling schemes and estimation methods. WP2 aims are thus to: (i) estimate N_e from both simulated datasets (with known true N_e values) and already accessible legacy datasets under known evolutionary scenarios, (ii) compare those N_e estimates across available methods and realistic sampling schemes, in order to (iii) provide best practices on how to proceed for obtaining reliable N_e indicators for GD reporting and monitoring in a large range of species.

- [D2.1 - Task T2.1 Compiling legacy datasets and designing evolutionary](#) - choose a limited number of legacy datasets representing species with different life cycles and spatial landscape settings. These will help first to select evolutionary scenarios that are customised for legacy datasets. Second, we will add other realistic scenarios for species representative of WP3 databases, and third include well-known theoretical models. We will use forward-in-time simulators as they allow controlling complex interactions across the main evolutionary factors. This is feasible with limited risk, due to recently developed software such as the flexible and generalist QuantiNemo2, SLIM3, and gMetapop, which also includes an independent graphical user interface with an age-class structure. For example, any level of dispersal capacity and isolation-by-distance patterns can be modelled using spatial grid frameworks.
- [D2.2 - Task T2.2 Model validation](#) - will validate the chosen modelling frameworks and scenario parameter values will be validated by verifying simulated GD outputs, and different types of N_e parameter true values at single population or metapopulation levels. These true N_e values are known from simulation results or derived from population genetics models (e.g. for complex scenarios with overlapping generations). We will use software extending the theoretical framework of N_e estimation to subdivided populations and variable migration rates (GESP or generational overlap (NEOGEN)).
- [D2.3 - Task 2.3 Sensitivity analysis of \$N_e\$ estimates](#) - Based on simulation results with known N_e , life history traits and spatial structure, we will (i) quantify the sensitivity of multiple N_e estimates to departures from method assumptions, (ii) test which sampling strategy could increase N_e accuracy, and how to adapt them to different scenarios, and (iii) compare monitoring schemes for detecting potential decline in N_e . Targeted resampling of legacy datasets will further corroborate optimal sampling of individuals and genetic data for N_e estimation and monitoring. Findings from these tasks will be valued in at least two publications, both focusing on the impact on N_e estimates of (a) population subdivision in models and experimental data, and (b) sampling schemes in contrasted case studies.
- [D2.4 - Task 2.4 Integration of datasets and methods into EBV workflows](#) - a set of configuration files representing generic

scenarios across different species or customised case studies, associated simulated datasets, standalone tools and scripts for computing the most appropriate scenario-dependent Ne estimates and diversity statistics will be presented to Nature Managers and Research stakeholders. These resources will be integrated into genetic EBV workflows developed in WP5 and therefore guide the decision-making process for both GD sampling and monitoring strategies in natural populations.

- **WP3 : Evaluating genetic indicators by using existing data sources** (Lead: Joachim Mergeay, Gernot Segelbacher) will explore how to best use existing data sources to estimate genetic indicators accepted in the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework. A recent pilot project targeting four European and five non-European countries is trying out the indicators [14] along with a draft data submission form and draft data extraction guidelines. The outcomes displayed which features of the methodology and data management need refining to make the indicators operable and comparable at a global scale. We will focus on publicly available existing data sources such as citizen-science fed species observation portals, papers and reports providing Ne data or Nc data as a proxy of Ne, or data that can be used to estimate Nc indirectly (area of occurrence, species distributions), and Red List source data. As we go down this Ne proxy cascade, the accuracy of the Ne estimate decreases, but the data availability and potential for comprehensive large scale assessments increases. We will explore how to best exploit this trade-off and optimise the workflow for indicator assessments.
 - [D3.1 - Task 3.1 Select species and compile data sources per country](#) - We will select species in dialogue with national/regional stakeholders for species of policy and management priority. These data will be used to derive population size estimates and population boundaries for selected species.
 - [D3.2 - Task 3.2 Determine population boundaries and estimate genetic](#) - From these data GD indicator 1 and indicator 2 can then be calculated and the suitability of the genetic indicators tested in different countries.
 - [D3.3 - Task 3.3 / 3.4 Improve workflows for data collection, indicator assessment](#) - A workflow will be developed together with stakeholders to ensure that the obtained data is easily accessible. The available information will help stakeholders (such as policy and nature management) to obtain genetic proxy data, especially in cases where no other genetic information is available. Interpretation of the derived proxy estimators will help stakeholders to fulfil their reporting duties to national and international bodies (such as the Convention on Biological Diversity). We will provide case studies and national assessments prioritising countries involved in GINAMO. The outcome of our analyses will complement existing biodiversity monitoring schemes e.g. the European Bird Census Council (EBCC) or the European Butterfly Monitoring Scheme (eBMS) and biodiversity data storage initiatives such as e.g. the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) and add relevant genetic data to

these ongoing initiatives.

- **WP4 : Evaluating satellite Earth observation data to generate proxies for GD** (Lead: Linda Laikre) will 1) to explore the use of satellite Earth observation to generate proxy data for assessing GD indicators (Indicator 1 and 2), and 2) to provide strategies for how such Earth observation-based proxy assessments can best be co-created with stakeholders and end-users. With this novel Earth observation-based approach, WP4 will significantly contribute to new ways of monitoring biodiversity. Recent work demonstrates that Earth observation can aid in assessing species richness. This is because variables that Earth observation can retrieve include habitat fragmentation, structural connectivity, and patch availability Earth observation can improve input parameters for species distribution models and macrogenetic studies, for assessing current and future habitats. For example, satellite Earth observation has been successfully used to derive estimates of habitat properties of importance for species diversity. Such assessments have been applied to assess species richness in grasslands in Sweden.
 - **D4.1 - Task 4.1 Generate earth observation-based proxies for assessing GD** - We hypothesise that these properties, which can be gathered from Earth observation, can also be used to estimate variables of importance for assessing GD indicators. We envision that this can be done as follows; habitat types (e.g., grasslands, forests, etc), suitable for specific species, the spatial distribution and connectivity is assessed with Earth observation data. This data is then combined with data on species specific densities over such suitable habitats to estimate the potential census size N_c and evaluate threshold values for N_c and N_e (WP3). We will focus our work on Sweden using data from the Swedish National Space Agency. We will use multispectral and hyperspectral Earth observation to map selected terrestrial habitats retrieving landscape indicators correlating with number of distinct populations and their N_c for selected species leveraging the European Copernicus system and preparing for future satellite missions such as CHIMES. Using artificial intelligence-based algorithms, trained on geolocated datasets of N_c , we will demonstrate how open Earth observation datasets can be used to provide wider aerial coverage quickly and efficiently. These outputs will help optimise monitoring schemes and best practices for using proxy indicators of GD (WP3). Earth observation as a proxy for GD, is poorly used in conservation management due to knowledge gaps.
 - **D4.2 - Task 4.2 Strategies for the use of earth observation-based proxies in** - To address these gaps, WP4 is based on close collaboration between research, policy and management and encompasses co-creation of strategies and tools to ensure that the new Earth observation-based assessment methods are relevant, applicable, and user-friendly. This will be possible to accomplish with our multidisciplinary team with expertise in social sciences (also with experience from assessing GD understanding and knowledge), population genetics, Earth observation techniques, landscape ecology, and conservation. The co-creative activities will be run in Sweden and

encompass focused workshops where researchers and stakeholders, together learn, explore and assess the new tools. This approach will be evaluated through interviews, focus groups and surveys to enhance knowledge on how participatory processes can aid in applying the Earth observation tools for GD monitoring. These focused workshops will be specialized, differently organized, and involve other participants than, and form the groundwork for inclusion of the Earth observation component in, the broader workshops of WP6. Knowledge gained in WP4 will feed into and further enhance WP3, WP5, and WP6. We envision 3-4 peer-reviewed scientific articles to be produced by WP4.

- **WP5 : EBV workflows for FAIR and Open Science** (Lead: Myriam Heuertz) underlines the need to 1) collect, preserve and share FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable) data on species and ecosystems before they are lost to the scientific record, and 2) provide standardised workflows producing biodiversity indicators to equip researchers, nature managers and policy makers with robust information and evidence on the complex dynamics of biodiversity. To implement data integration (linking data sources using the Galaxy platform initiative) and workflow operationalization, we have partnered with EBVOSC, a pilot initiative led by the Pôle National de Données de Biodiversité of French BON focused on operationalisation of EBV workflows.
 - [D5.1 - Task 5.1 Data management plan on simulated and observed biotic](#) - With guidance from EBVOSC, WP5 will establish a data management plan for the simulated and observed biotic and abiotic data of GINAMO.
 - [D5.2 - Task 5.2 Data integration from WP2 to WP4 into Galaxy](#) - WP5 will liaise with data stakeholders to integrate various data types, including genetic and genotypic data (from WP2), Ne and Nc estimates, metadata on life history traits (from WP3) and abiotic data such as spatially explicit habitat suitability data or SDMs (from WP4).
 - [D5.3 / 5.4 - Task 5.3 / 5.4 Development of EBV workflows for genetic data and proxy data](#) - WP5 will then use the best practice recommendations from WP2-4 and research and management stakeholder interests and needs expressed in joint workshops (WP6) to develop standardised and user-friendly EBV workflows based on genetic and proxy data in agreement with FAIR principles [38] and Open Science practices. EBV workflows could include for example (1) radio buttons for choosing one reference or simulated dataset (among many available based on conservation interests, and defined by their metadata, from WP2 or WP3), one among previously discussed sampling schemes (with Nature Managers), one Ne estimation method, (2) running the automatic resampling of a data subset, which (3) serves as input in the method, (4) finally, a conclusion is provided on the Ne accuracy (i.e. closeness to the true value), which (5) helps for deciding on best monitoring strategies. EBV workflows will include options for customizable reports to meet management stakeholders' needs for reporting on genetic indicators. We will use the 2021-2023 BiodiFAIRse GO FAIR IN implementation network in an open data portal supported by

GBIF and Galaxy. Workflow operationalisation will consist in script customisation, managing, archiving and sharing of source code, user- friendly and reproducible interactive running of code, results and visualisations for publication, in line with the DataOne network of data catalogues. Using existing standards such as Ecological Metadata Language (EML) to produce rich associated Metadata and the Darwin-core standard will facilitate reaching a high level of FAIRness and openness in disseminating data and metadata in appropriate international data banks such as GBIF, DataONE or Genbank and EBI SRA. Technical publications on EBV workflows will contribute to their dissemination.

- **WP6 : Co-creating strategies** (Lead: Peter Galbusera, Alexander Kopatz) will address how a framework to monitor GD (WP2-5) is best co-created to result in efficient action.
 - [D6.1 - Task T6.1](#) - WP6 will engage stakeholders in five countries (Belgium, Denmark, France, Italy and Sweden), representing different European biogeographic regions as well as governance and management systems, in co-creating processes that include two workshops per country, complemented with short online meetings and written communication.
 - [D6.2 - Task T6.2](#) - Our social scientists will study the effects of the process on participants’ knowledge, perceived usefulness of genetic indicators and willingness to implement them.

Fields of science and technology (from OECD classification)

Biological sciences (Natural sciences), 1.5 Earth and related environmental sciences

Language

eng

Creation date

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2024-07-25

Identifier

Identifier type

DOI

License

Name

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International

URL

<http://spdx.org/licenses/CC-BY-4.0.json>

Associated documents (publications, reports, patents, experimental plan...), website

- Biodiversa data management guide : [10.5281/zenodo.3448251](https://zenodo.org/record/3448251)

Project Details

Project title

Genetic Indicators for Nature Monitoring

Acronym

GINAMO

Abstract

The ongoing biodiversity crisis imperils Nature’s Contributions to

People and is being exacerbated by climate change. Genetic diversity within species is key to maintaining adaptive potential and ecosystem resilience, and is one of the three pillars of biodiversity, but is widely ignored in both policy and management, due to knowledge and implementation gaps.

In **GINAMO**, we follow a co-creation process to provide clear scientific guidelines and ready-to-use workflows to estimate genetic indicators that are understood and embraced by end users. Two indicators in the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework are appropriate for monitoring and reporting on genetic diversity. These indicators relate a) to a minimum effective population size, N_e , of 500, with N_e being an essential biodiversity variable enabling the quantification of genetic diversity loss, and b) to maintain genetically distinct populations within species.

In **GINAMO** we first will determine best practices to obtain accurate and robust N_e estimates for species with reference DNA-based data (WP2). Genetic data will help designing realistic evolutionary scenarios for simulations, to understand how spatial distributions, life history traits, data quantity and types, sampling strategies and statistical methods affect N_e estimates. For species without DNA-based data available, in WP3 and WP4 we will develop best practices to estimate N_e from proxies with publicly available data sources (e.g population size counts, occurrence data in observation portals, and relevant terrestrial habitat properties generated by earth observation data).

A key component in **GINAMO** is to partner and co-decide from the outset with the stakeholder community for an optimal integration of all resources produced from WP2 to WP4 activities (i.e. databases, scripts, and guidelines) to meet their concerns, reporting duties and monitoring needs. Standardised and automated workflows will be co-created for assessing genetic indicators on various transboundary geographical scales, following FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable) principles (WP5).

The impact of the co-creation processes on participants' knowledge, perceived usefulness of genetic indicators and willingness to implement, will be evaluated through interviews, focus groups and surveys (WP6). This co-creation process will strongly benefit from the multidisciplinary research team, including both natural and social scientists with expertise in policy and implementation.

GINAMO effectively fits all three themes of the call as it will integrate various sources of available data in existing biodiversity databases (Theme 3) to address knowledge gaps (Theme 2) and provide outreach materials and Open Science tools for genetic indicators applicable in international (e.g. EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030) and national policies, to improve new biodiversity data collection and inform specific conservation management actions (Theme 1).

Funding

- Agence Nationale de la Recherche : ANR-23-EBIP-0003-06
- French National Research Agency : ANR-23-EBIP-0003
- French National Research Agency : ANR-23-EBIP-0003

Start date

2024-03-01

End date

2027-02-28

Partners

- Institut national de recherche pour l'agriculture, l'alimentation et l'environnement <https://ror.org/003vg9w96>
- Copenhagen Zoo <https://ror.org/019950a73>
- Eigen vermogen van het instituut voor natuur- en bosonderzoek <https://ror.org/00j54wy13>
- Stockholm University <https://ror.org/05f0yaq80>
- University of Freiburg <https://ror.org/0245cg223>
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- Norwegian Institute for Nature Research <https://ror.org/04aha0598>
- Koninklijke Nederlandse Maatschappij voor Diergeneeskunde <https://ror.org/006rga838>
- Fondazione Edmund Mach <https://ror.org/0381bab64>
- Luleå University of Technology <https://ror.org/016st3p78>
- Morton Arboretum <https://ror.org/016s23c19>
- Biodiversité, Gènes et Communautés

Research outputs :

1. GINAMO full data management plan (Text)
2. List of configuration files for simulations across representative scenarios (Text)
3. List of legacy genetic datasets with access and metadata information (Dataset)
4. Report on the influence of species spatial distribution, genetic structure and life-history traits on N_e estimates (Text)
5. Guidelines for optimal sampling when inferring N_e in species with contrasted distributions and traits (Text)
6. Ready-to-use workflows on sampling and monitoring strategies in species with various N_e and spatial distributions (Workflow)
7. Review paper on N_e/N_c ratios (Text)
8. Datasets and reports of country's assessment for GBIF (Dataset)
9. Overview paper reporting on the assessment process for GD indicators (Text)
10. Workflow guidelines for assessment of indicators (Text)
11. Earth observation indicators of species distributions and N_c co- developed with stakeholders (Dataset)
12. Simulated and observed biotic and abiotic data (Dataset)
13. Data integration using simulated or observed genetic data (Workflow)
14. Genetic EBV workflow using genetic data (Workflow)
15. Genetic EBV workflow using proxy data (Workflow)
16. Scientific report on the effects of the co-creation process (Text)
17. Four outreach materials (StoryMaps, videos, arts, games) (Other)

Contributors

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"Genetic Indicators for NAture Monitoring" DMP

GINAMO full data management plan

Data description and collection or re-use of existing data

Research output description

Name	GINAMO full data management plan
Description	Full data management plan for GINAMO, integrating and including management of WP5 data (simulated genetic data, reused genetic and proxy data, and newly generated code) and the survey and data from WP6 on social sciences.
Type	Text
Workpackage	T1.2 - Conceive GINAMO's data management plan
Language	eng
Issued Date	
May contain personal data?	No
May contain sensible data?	No

Will existing data be reused?

Justification	See All Deliverables (D1.1, D2.1, D2.2, D2.3, D2.4, D3.1, D3.2, D3.3, D3.4, D4.1, D5.1, D5.2, D5.3, D5.4)
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How new data will be collected or produced?

Documentation and data quality

What metadata and documentation (for example way of organising data) will accompany the data?

Description

Data description and metadata generation will be started at the time of data collection to ensure the (re)usability of data. The proper documentation and metadata will ensure the smooth repository/archive storage of data and the findability of published data.

Data(sets) will be documented with descriptive metadata as required, e.g., each data set will include metadata about data ownership, creators and access rights. Data files are also named using the necessary information to distinguish between the files when necessary.

The extra documentation, e.g., README files or workflow documentation, will also be created about the data and processing of data whenever it is necessary to ensure the usability and understandability of the data.

The usability and interoperability of data intended to be openly available or to be shared with third parties in another way is guaranteed by using commonly used or non-proprietary formats. It is also essential from the point of view of sharing, findability and understandability of data that the repositories/archives where we will publish open data support the provision of comprehensive metadata and documentation.

The instructions to collect/generate data on standard bases, metadata production, documentation and data opening will be provided as necessary and will be available in the shared repository used by the consortium (Nextcloud or other storage space)

File format in which the data is stored. This follows the most widely used convention in the discipline that conform to the international standards (based on the KNAW-DANS Preferred Formats overview, November 2015) to ensure future compatibility. These includes:

- Document (.txt; .pdf; .doc; .docx; .odt)
- Spreadsheet (.csv; xls; .xlsx; .ods)
- GIS shapefile (.shp + tables)
- GIS raster data (.geotif; .img)
- Database (.sql; .mdb; .accdb)
- Picture (.jpg; .tif; .png)
- Audio (.wav; mp3)
- Video (.avi; .mp4; .mov)

What methods will be used to ensure their scientific quality?

Legal and ethical requirements, codes of conduct

How will other legal issues, such as intellectual property rights and ownership, be managed? What legislation is applicable?

Description

The data produced by the project will be made openly available always when possible and useful for re-users. This will be done in accordance with ethical guidelines and applicable legislation, such as the EU's General data protection regulation (GDPR), and respecting ownership and terms of use.

Data(sets) will be documented with descriptive metadata as required, e.g., each data set will include metadata about data ownership, creators and access rights.

TRUE or not ? -> So far, we have recognised that only interview data and remote sensing images cannot be made publicly available in our project.

What ethical issues and codes of conduct are there, and how will they be taken into account?

Description

- **This activity involve processing of personal data.** We will conduct stakeholder surveys that comply with the EU GDPR, and under the approval of the Norwegian Centre for Research Data (<https://www.nsd.no/en>).
- **This activity involve the development, deployment and/or use of Artificial Intelligence.** The research will include the development and use of machine learning image classification algorithms. Machine Learning (ML) is an AI related computer technology in wide use in remote sensing and statistics. ML uses training data to teach the algorithm how to recognise features. We will not use images of humans nor will we use AIs with personal data. We therefore see no ethical issues in our uses of ML classifiers.

Data processing and analysis

How and with what resources will the data be processed / analyzed?

Storage and backup during the research process

How will data be stored and backed up during the research?

Storage needs

Data and all other materials will be stored on password-protected servers, accessible only to authorised persons. The storage and proper management of the original data is the responsibility of the partner who collects the data in question or is responsible for processing the data.

Once the original data has been classified, analysed, summarised, or otherwise processed into an agreed common format, it is reported to and shared with the partners. Data can also be shared with partners using other services such as data archives/repositories and databases as appropriate.

To keep oversight of data and ensure the quality, findability and usability, we follow good data storage practices: The data will be organised according to the data specific procedures and associated with the necessary information/ metadata to understand the data, taking advantage of the features of each storage/sharing system. In case of data files proper file naming procedures are used to distinguish between the files.

[Describe here which kind of data will be stored and shared through open data archives/repositories \(SRA, others repositories\)](#)

Solutions regarding the total volume of project data

If the INRAE NEXTCLOUD solution is chosen, it will depend on the volume of storage envisaged (<1To or >1To) and whether or not all the partners are part of the identity federation.

As far as volume is concerned, if it's <1TB, it's easily possible, but you'll need to request a Nextcloud space dedicated to the project, which INRAE will manage for the group. To date, there is no charge for this service.

If the volume is >1TB, you'll need to specify how much and for which file types. This service would be invoiced, as it can be set up by a partner.

As for access to project partners, there is always a way of granting access: https://nextcloud.inrae.fr/core/doc/user/acces_non_INRAE.html whether or not they are part of the identity federation, but it's easier if all partners are.

It is recommend that partners keep at least two copies of backups in external drives to ensure data safety by avoiding risks of accidental deletion or failure of hard drives. It is recommended to keep at least two copies of backups in external drives.

Estimated volume of data

1

Unit

TB

Data sharing and long-term preservation

How will data be shared?

Modalities of sharing

Data sharing describes whether and how data will be shared. Proposed categories :

- destroyed after end project
- not shared
- not shared but preserved
- shared upon request
- openly shared

Reusability

How will data be long-term preserved? Which data?

List of configuration files for simulations across representative scenarios

Data description and collection or re-use of existing data

Research output description

Name	List of configuration files for simulations across representative scenarios
Description	We will use forward-in-time simulators as they allow controlling complex interactions across the main evolutionary factors. Configuration files will be constructed for (simulators) based on metadata from legacy datasets. Lists of legacy datasets and their metadata will be deposited on Zenodo.
Type	Text
Workpackage	T2.1 - Compiling legacy datasets and designing evolutionary
Keywords (free-text)	
Language	eng
Issued Date	2024-12-31
May contain personal data?	No
May contain sensible data?	No
May take ethical issues into account?	Yes

Will existing data be reused?

Justification	non-reuse of existing data
----------------------	----------------------------

How new data will be collected or produced?

Name of the method	Creation of configuration files
Description	Describe how the configuration files will be generated ?
Data Nature	Simulation

Documentation and data quality

What metadata and documentation (for example way of organising data) will accompany the data?

Description

Describe here organization, structuration and documentation of the **configuration files**

An internal project ID number is assigned to each data item. The ID number uses the following naming rule: **Date-WP-PartnerAcronym-configuration-FileName**

Internal id	Description	Source	Type	File format	Volume	Sensitive
2024-05-25-WP2-INRAE-configuration-File1	Configuration file 1 with species ...	Salguero Gomez 2015	Numeric / Text / ...	Ex : csv	< 1MB	Yes / No

Metadata language code eng

What methods will be used to ensure their scientific quality?

Legal and ethical requirements, codes of conduct

How will other legal issues, such as intellectual property rights and ownership, be managed? What legislation is applicable?

What ethical issues and codes of conduct are there, and how will they be taken into account?

Question sans réponse.

Data processing and analysis

How and with what resources will the data be processed / analyzed?

Storage and backup during the research process

How will data be stored and backed up during the research?

Storage needs	Low volume required to store these configuration files. In general, need to set up a common file storage space for the project (Nextcloud INRAE, other?).
Estimated volume of data	50
Unit	MB
Measures taken for data security	Use of secure, backed-up servers (INRAE ?)

Data sharing and long-term preservation

How will data be shared?

Modalities of sharing	The configuration files will be generated and stored locally by the partners. Data that has been classified in a uniform format and/or processed is shared with the project partners using appropriate tools or spaces ((Nextcloud INRAE, Google Drive, others ?)
Reusability	yes

How will data be long-term preserved? Which data?

Justification	No Long term preservation
Unit	
Start date	
End date	
Final dispositions	

List of legacy genetic datasets with access and metadata information

Data description and collection or re-use of existing data

Research output description

Name	List of legacy genetic datasets with access and metadata information
Description	<p>This list contains the access information and metadata of already accessible legacy genetic datasets used in the project. The list is available as a table at the following link: List of legacy datasets.</p> <p>The metadata are contained in the list, see README tab in the linked spreadsheet. Once consolidated, this list will be available on Zenodo with a doi identifier, using document versioning.</p>
Type	Dataset
Workpackage	WP2, WP3, WP6
Keywords (free-text)	
Language	english
Issued Date	2024-07-01
Persistent identifier	
Identifier type	DOI
May contain personal data?	No
May contain sensible data?	No
May take ethical issues into account?	Yes

Will existing data be reused?

Justification Yes, this Research output rests entirely on the re-use of available data, as foreseen in the project description (WP2, WP3). See response to 1.1. (Briefly describe...)

How new data will be collected or produced?

Documentation and data quality

What metadata and documentation (for example way of organising data) will accompany the data?

Description

The common storage spare is https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/17FziWYZMJ22s2VP-KrwwgyGHND_sjm1O?usp=sharing or DataINRAE or....?
A dedicated folder named "Legacy datasets" contains subfolders corresponding to each of the legacy datasets. More information in D2.1.

Metadata/data standards

- Darwin Core : <https://rdamsc.bath.ac.uk/api2/m9>
- Darwin Core Geospatial Extension : <https://rdamsc.bath.ac.uk/api2/m54>
- EML (Ecological Metadata Language) : <https://rdamsc.bath.ac.uk/api2/m16>

Metadata language code english

Documentation software Darwin Core Archive Assistant, Dataverse

What methods will be used to ensure their scientific quality?**Description**

Published genomic data will be accessed. Filtered vcf files will be used. Filters will be used based on GATK best practices in the case of whole genome resequencing data.
A workflow for data quality will be made available (on Github?).

Legal and ethical requirements, codes of conduct

How will other legal issues, such as intellectual property rights and ownership, be managed? What legislation is applicable?

What ethical issues and codes of conduct are there, and how will they be taken into account?

Data processing and analysis

How and with what resources will the data be processed / analyzed?

Storage and backup during the research process

How will data be stored and backed up during the research?

Storage needs	We will need a shared space for 54 legacy datasets, for which we will store a filtered genomic genotype matrix, generally under vcf format, corresponding to approx. 100 individuals x 100 000 SNPs. This amounts to an estimated data volume of 100 Gb. https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/17FziWYZMJ22s2VP-KrwwgyGHND_sjm1O?usp=sharing
Estimated volume of data	150
Unit	GB
Measures taken for data security	Use of secure, backed-up servers (INRAE NEXTCLOUD PLATFORM ?)

Data sharing and long-term preservation

How will data be shared?

Modalities of sharing In a first step, the **legacy datasets** will be generated and stored locally by the partners (NAS, NextCloud INRAE).
Final sharing will be done on Zenodo, Dataverse, GitHub / GitLab.

Reusability

Data repository/catalogs

- Zenodo : <https://cat.opidor.fr/index.php/Zenodo> ()

How will data be long-term preserved? Which data?

Justification Final archiving will be done on Zenodo, SWH.
See 6.1

Estimated volume of data 100

Unit GB

Start date

End date

Archive

Title Software Heritage
Repository ID https://cat.opidor.fr/index.php/Software_Heritage
Identifier type URL
Geo location (country) FR
Certification
PID system SWHID
Available metadata standards

Final dispositions

Report on the influence of species spatial distribution, genetic structure and life-history traits on Ne estimates

Data description and collection or re-use of existing data

Research output description

Name Report on the influence of species spatial distribution, genetic structure and life-history traits on Ne estimates

Description The chosen modelling frameworks and scenario parameter values will be validated by verifying simulated GD outputs, and different types of Ne parameter true values at single population or metapopulation levels.

Describe the way to validate frameworks and scenario parameter values

Type Text

Workpackage T2.2 - Model validation

Issued Date

May contain personal data? No

May contain sensible data? No

May take ethical issues into account? No

Will existing data be reused?

Question sans réponse.

How new data will be collected or produced?

Question sans réponse.

Documentation and data quality

What metadata and documentation (for example way of organising data) will accompany the data?

Description

Describe the way to validate frameworks and scenario parameter values, standards and metadata used

What methods will be used to ensure their scientific quality?

Question sans réponse.

Legal and ethical requirements, codes of conduct

How will other legal issues, such as intellectual property rights and ownership, be managed? What legislation is applicable?

Question sans réponse.

What ethical issues and codes of conduct are there, and how will they be taken into account?

Question sans réponse.

Data processing and analysis

How and with what resources will the data be processed / analyzed?

Description

Describe the processes to validate frameworks and scenario parameter values

Storage and backup during the research process

How will data be stored and backed up during the research?

Question sans réponse.

Data sharing and long-term preservation

How will data be shared?

Question sans réponse.

How will data be long-term preserved? Which data?

Question sans réponse.

Guidelines for optimal sampling when inferring N_e in species with contrasted distributions and traits

Data description and collection or re-use of existing data

Research output description

Name	Guidelines for optimal sampling when inferring N_e in species with contrasted distributions and traits
Description	Based on simulation results with known N_e , life history traits and spatial structure, we will <ul style="list-style-type: none">• quantify the sensitivity of multiple N_e estimates to departures from method assumptions• test which sampling strategy could increase N_e accuracy, and how to adapt them to different scenarios• compare monitoring schemes for detecting potential decline in N_e
Type	Text
Workpackage	T2.3 - Sensitivity analysis of N_e estimates
Keywords (free-text)	
Issued Date	
May contain personal data?	No
May contain sensible data?	No
May take ethical issues into account?	No

Will existing data be reused?

How new data will be collected or produced?

Documentation and data quality

What metadata and documentation (for example way of organising data) will accompany the data?

Description

Describe methods, metadata, documentation to :

- quantify the sensitivity of multiple Ne estimates to departures from method assumptions
- test which sampling strategy could increase Ne accuracy, and how to adapt them to different scenarios
- compare monitoring schemes for detecting potential decline in Ne

What methods will be used to ensure their scientific quality?

Question sans réponse.

Legal and ethical requirements, codes of conduct**How will other legal issues, such as intellectual property rights and ownership, be managed? What legislation is applicable?**

Question sans réponse.

What ethical issues and codes of conduct are there, and how will they be taken into account?

Question sans réponse.

Data processing and analysis**How and with what resources will the data be processed / analyzed?**

Question sans réponse.

Storage and backup during the research process

How will data be stored and backed up during the research?

Data sharing and long-term preservation

How will data be shared?

Question sans réponse.

How will data be long-term preserved? Which data?

Question sans réponse.

Ready-to-use workflows on sampling and monitoring strategies in species with various Ne and spatial distributions

Data description and collection or re-use of existing data

Research output description

Name	Ready-to-use workflows on sampling and monitoring strategies in species with various Ne and spatial distributions
Description	A set of configuration files representing generic scenarios across different species or customised case studies, associated simulated datasets, standalone tools and scripts for computing the most appropriate scenario-dependent Ne estimates and diversity statistics will be created and presented to Nature Managers and Research stakeholders.
Type	Workflow
Workpackage	T2.4 - Integration of datasets and methods into EBV workflows
Language	eng
Issued Date	
May contain personal data?	No
May contain sensible data?	No
May take ethical issues into account?	No

Will existing data be reused?

Justification These resources will be integrated into genetic EBV workflows developed in WP5 (D5.2)

How new data will be collected or produced?

Name of the method Workflows development
Data Nature Simulation

Documentation and data quality

What metadata and documentation (for example way of organising data) will accompany the data?

Question sans réponse.

What methods will be used to ensure their scientific quality?

Question sans réponse.

Legal and ethical requirements, codes of conduct

How will other legal issues, such as intellectual property rights and ownership, be managed? What legislation is applicable?

Question sans réponse.

What ethical issues and codes of conduct are there, and how will they be taken into account?

Question sans réponse.

Data processing and analysis

How and with what resources will the data be processed / analyzed?

Question sans réponse.

Storage and backup during the research process

How will data be stored and backed up during the research?

Data sharing and long-term preservation

How will data be shared?

Question sans réponse.

How will data be long-term preserved? Which data?

Question sans réponse.

Review paper on N e /N c ratios

Data description and collection or re-use of existing data

Research output description

Name	Review paper on N e /N c ratios
Description	Selection of species in dialogue with national/regional stakeholders for species of policy and management priority. These data will be used to derive population size estimates and population boundaries for selected species. Review paper on Ne/Nc ratios
Type	Text
Workpackage	T3.1 - Select species and compile data sources per country
Keywords (free-text)	
Language	eng
Issued Date	
May contain personal data?	No
May contain sensible data?	No
May take ethical issues into account?	No

Will existing data be reused?

Justification Possibly yes

How new data will be collected or produced?

Name of the method

Description Use of existing data, no data collection or acquisition

Data Nature Observation

Documentation and data quality

What metadata and documentation (for example way of organising data) will accompany the data?

Description

Describe here organization, structuration and documentation of the **species files**. An internal project ID number is assigned to each data item. The ID number uses the following naming rule: **Date-WP-PartnerAcronym-species-FileName**

Internal id	Description	Source	Type	File format	Volume	Sensitive
2024-05-25-WP2-INRAE-species-File1	File with species ...		Numeric / Text / ...	Ex : csv	< 1MB	Yes / No

Review paper on Ne/Nc ratios

What methods will be used to ensure their scientific quality?

Question sans réponse.

Legal and ethical requirements, codes of conduct

How will other legal issues, such as intellectual property rights and ownership, be managed? What legislation is applicable?

Question sans réponse.

What ethical issues and codes of conduct are there, and how will they be taken into account?

Question sans réponse.

Data processing and analysis

How and with what resources will the data be processed / analyzed?

Question sans réponse.

Storage and backup during the research process

How will data be stored and backed up during the research?

Estimated volume of data	1
Unit	MB

Data sharing and long-term preservation

How will data be shared?

Question sans réponse.

How will data be long-term preserved? Which data?

Question sans réponse.

Datasets and reports of country's assessment for GBIF

Data description and collection or re-use of existing data

Research output description

Name	Datasets and reports of country's assessment for GBIF
Description	From data provided by T3.1, GD indicator 1 and indicator 2 can be calculated and the suitability of the genetic indicators tested in different countries (T3.2). Datasets and reports of country's assessment for GBIF.
Type	Dataset
Workpackage	T3.2 - Determine population boundaries and estimate genetic indicators for each species
Language	eng
Issued Date	
May contain personal data?	No
May contain sensible data?	No
May take ethical issues into account?	No

Will existing data be reused?

Question sans réponse.

How new data will be collected or produced?

Question sans réponse.

Documentation and data quality

What metadata and documentation (for example way of organising data) will accompany the data?

Description

Describe how the calculation will be made / write the calculation procedure with metadata + documentation / Datasets and reports of country's assessment for GBIF

What methods will be used to ensure their scientific quality?

Question sans réponse.

Legal and ethical requirements, codes of conduct

How will other legal issues, such as intellectual property rights and ownership, be managed? What legislation is applicable?

Question sans réponse.

What ethical issues and codes of conduct are there, and how will they be taken into account?

Question sans réponse.

Data processing and analysis

How and with what resources will the data be processed / analyzed?

Question sans réponse.

Storage and backup during the research process

How will data be stored and backed up during the research?

Estimated volume of data	100
Unit	MB

Data sharing and long-term preservation

How will data be shared?

Question sans réponse.

How will data be long-term preserved? Which data?

Question sans réponse.

Overview paper reporting on the assessment process for GD indicators

Data description and collection or re-use of existing data

Research output description

Name	Overview paper reporting on the assessment process for GD indicators
Description	A workflow will be developed together with stakeholders to ensure that the obtained data is easily accessible. Overview paper reporting on the assessment process for GD indicators
Type	Text
Workpackage	T3.3 - Evaluate and improve workflows for data collection, indicator assessment and indicator reporting
Language	eng
Issued Date	
May contain personal data?	No
May contain sensible data?	No
May take ethical issues into account?	No

Will existing data be reused?

Justification Workflows can be reused for new implementation or modification

How new data will be collected or produced?

Question sans réponse.

Documentation and data quality

What metadata and documentation (for example way of organising data) will accompany the data?

Description Describe the workflow steps, tools used, metadata, controlled vocabularies or ontologies / thesauri + documentation.
Overview paper reporting on the assessment process for GD indicators

What methods will be used to ensure their scientific quality?

Legal and ethical requirements, codes of conduct

How will other legal issues, such as intellectual property rights and ownership, be managed? What legislation is applicable?

Question sans réponse.

What ethical issues and codes of conduct are there, and how will they be taken into account?

Question sans réponse.

Data processing and analysis

How and with what resources will the data be processed / analyzed?

Question sans réponse.

Storage and backup during the research process

How will data be stored and backed up during the research?

Question sans réponse.

Data sharing and long-term preservation

How will data be shared?

Question sans réponse.

How will data be long-term preserved? Which data?

Question sans réponse.

Workflow guidelines for assessment of indicators

Data description and collection or re-use of existing data

Research output description

Name	Workflow guidelines for assessment of indicators
Description	Workflow guidelines for assessment of indicators
Type	Text
Workpackage	
Issued Date	
May contain personal data?	No

Will existing data be reused?

Question sans réponse.

How new data will be collected or produced?

Question sans réponse.

Documentation and data quality

What metadata and documentation (for example way of organising data) will accompany the data?

Description

Workflow guidelines for assessment of indicators.

What methods will be used to ensure their scientific quality?

Question sans réponse.

Legal and ethical requirements, codes of conduct

How will other legal issues, such as intellectual property rights and ownership, be managed? What legislation is applicable?

Question sans réponse.

What ethical issues and codes of conduct are there, and how will they be taken into account?

Question sans réponse.

Data processing and analysis

How and with what resources will the data be processed / analyzed?

Storage and backup during the research process

How will data be stored and backed up during the research?

Estimated volume of data	10
Unit	MB

Data sharing and long-term preservation

How will data be shared?

How will data be long-term preserved? Which data?

Question sans réponse.

Earth observation indicators of species distributions and Nc co-developed with stakeholders

Data description and collection or re-use of existing data

Research output description

Name	Earth observation indicators of species distributions and Nc co- developed with stakeholders
Description	<p>Explore the use of satellite Earth observation to generate proxy data for assessing GD indicators. Information gathered from Earth observation can be used to estimate variables of importance for assessing GD indicators.</p> <p>We will focus our work on Sweden using data from the Swedish National Space Agency. We will use multispectral and hyperspectral Earth observation to map selected terrestrial habitats retrieving landscape indicators correlating with number of distinct populations and their Nc for selected species leveraging the European Copernicus system and preparing for future satellite missions such as CHIMES. Using artificial intelligence-based algorithms, trained on geolocated datasets of Nc, we will demonstrate how open Earth observation datasets can be used to provide wider aerial coverage quickly and efficiently. These outputs will help optimise monitoring schemes and best practices for using proxy indicators of GD.</p>
Type	Dataset
Workpackage	T4.1 - Exploring the use of Earth observation to generate proxy data for assessing GD indicators
Language	eng
Issued Date	
May contain personal data?	No
May contain sensible data?	No
May take ethical issues into account?	No

Will existing data be reused?

Question sans réponse.

How new data will be collected or produced?

Question sans réponse.

Documentation and data quality

What metadata and documentation (for example way of organising data) will accompany the data?

Description

Describe here data from the Swedish National Space Agency (datasets, formats, metadata, ...)

What methods will be used to ensure their scientific quality?

Question sans réponse.

Legal and ethical requirements, codes of conduct

How will other legal issues, such as intellectual property rights and ownership, be managed? What legislation is applicable?

Question sans réponse.

What ethical issues and codes of conduct are there, and how will they be taken into account?

Question sans réponse.

Data processing and analysis

How and with what resources will the data be processed / analyzed?

Question sans réponse.

Storage and backup during the research process

How will data be stored and backed up during the research?

Question sans réponse.

Data sharing and long-term preservation

How will data be shared?

Question sans réponse.

How will data be long-term preserved? Which data?

Question sans réponse.

Simulated and observed biotic and abiotic data

Data description and collection or re-use of existing data

Research output description

Name	Simulated and observed biotic and abiotic data
Description	With guidance from EBVOSC, management and description of the simulated and observed biotic and abiotic data of GINAMO. Concerns most of the data described in the others tasks and deliverables.
Type	Dataset
Workpackage	T5.1 - Data management planning for EBV workflows
Language	eng
Issued Date	
May contain personal data?	No
May contain sensible data?	No
May take ethical issues into account?	No

Will existing data be reused?

How new data will be collected or produced?

Question sans réponse.

Documentation and data quality

What metadata and documentation (for example way of organising data) will accompany the data?

Description

See all deliverables concerning simulated and observed biotic and abiotic data of GINAMO (deliverables from WP2 and WP3)

We will use the 2021- 2023 BiodiFAIRse GO FAIR IN implementation network in an open data portal supported by GBIF and Galaxy.

Workflow operationalisation will consist in script customisation, managing, archiving and sharing of source code, user- friendly and reproducible interactive running of code, results and visualisations for publication, in line with the DataOne network of data catalogues.

Using existing standards such as **Ecological Metadata Language (EML)** to produce rich associated Metadata and the **Darwin-core standard** will facilitate reaching a high level of **FAIRness** and openness in disseminating data and metadata in appropriate international data banks such as **GBIF, DataONE or Genbank and EBI SRA**.

Technical publications on EBV workflows will contribute to their dissemination.

Metadata/data standards

- Darwin Core : <https://rdamsc.bath.ac.uk/api2/m9>
- Darwin Core Geospatial Extension : <https://rdamsc.bath.ac.uk/api2/m54>
- EML (Ecological Metadata Language) : <https://rdamsc.bath.ac.uk/api2/m16>

Metadata language code eng

What methods will be used to ensure their scientific quality?

Question sans réponse.

Legal and ethical requirements, codes of conduct

How will other legal issues, such as intellectual property rights and ownership, be managed? What legislation is applicable?

Question sans réponse.

What ethical issues and codes of conduct are there, and how will they be taken into account?

Question sans réponse.

Data processing and analysis

How and with what resources will the data be processed / analyzed?

Question sans réponse.

Storage and backup during the research process

How will data be stored and backed up during the research?

Question sans réponse.

Data sharing and long-term preservation

How will data be shared?

Question sans réponse.

How will data be long-term preserved? Which data?

Question sans réponse.

Data integration using simulated or observed genetic data

Data description and collection or re-use of existing data

Research output description

Name	Data integration using simulated or observed genetic data
Description	Integrate genetic and genotypic data from WP2, metadata on life history traits from WP3 and abiotic data such as spatially explicit habitat suitability data or SDMs from WP4, into Galaxy
Type	Workflow
Workpackage	T5.2 - Data integration from WP2 to WP4 into Galaxy
Language	eng
Issued Date	
May contain personal data?	No
May contain sensible data?	No
May take ethical issues into account?	No

Will existing data be reused?

Question sans réponse.

How new data will be collected or produced?

Question sans réponse.

Documentation and data quality

What metadata and documentation (for example way of organising data) will accompany the data?

Description Metadata and organisation of simulated or observed genetic data
Describe the way and methods to integrate these data

Metadata language code eng

What methods will be used to ensure their scientific quality?

Question sans réponse.

Legal and ethical requirements, codes of conduct

How will other legal issues, such as intellectual property rights and ownership, be managed? What legislation is applicable?

Question sans réponse.

What ethical issues and codes of conduct are there, and how will they be taken into account?

Question sans réponse.

Data processing and analysis

How and with what resources will the data be processed / analyzed?

Storage and backup during the research process

How will data be stored and backed up during the research?

Question sans réponse.

Data sharing and long-term preservation

How will data be shared?

Question sans réponse.

How will data be long-term preserved? Which data?

Question sans réponse.

Genetic EBV workflow using genetic data

Data description and collection or re-use of existing data

Research output description

Name	Genetic EBV workflow using genetic data
Description	<p>Co-development and validation of workflows with partners and Data Managers Development of EBV workflows for genetic data providing genetic and proxy data (WP2-WP4)</p> <p>Describe here and below the workflow</p> <p>EBV workflows could include for example (1) radio buttons for choosing one reference or simulated dataset (among many available based on conservation interests, and defined by their metadata, from WP2 or WP3), one Ne estimation method, (2) running the automatic resampling of a data subset, which (3) serves as input in the method, (4) finally, a conclusion is provided on the Ne accuracy (i.e. closeness to the true value), which (5) helps for deciding on best monitoring strategies.</p> <p>EBV workflow steps</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. RAW DATA Observations (Raw observations from surveys, sensors, satellite remote sensing, DNA, ..) 2. EBVs (Data sets with measurements and observation - Harmonized data sets - Data inter- or extrapolated or processed with statistical model) 3. Indicators (Changes in biodiversity)
Type	Workflow
Workpackage	T5.3 - Development of EBV workflows for genetic data
Keywords (free-text)	
Language	eng
Issued Date	
May contain personal data?	No
May contain sensible data?	No
May take ethical issues into account?	No

Will existing data be reused?

Justification Workflows can be reused for new implementation or modification

How new data will be collected or produced?

Question sans réponse.

Documentation and data quality

What metadata and documentation (for example way of organising data) will accompany the data?

Description**Use of Galaxy Platform, with four principle keys**

1. Accessibility
2. Reproducibility
3. Transparency
4. Peer review

EBV workflow steps

1. List of Necessary data and metadata to compute EBVs
2. Galaxy platform
3. Script atomization (several atomized R scripts for several input data files)
4. Script sharing (Toolshed)

Metadata language code eng

What methods will be used to ensure their scientific quality?

Question sans réponse.

Legal and ethical requirements, codes of conduct

How will other legal issues, such as intellectual property rights and ownership, be managed? What legislation is applicable?

Question sans réponse.

What ethical issues and codes of conduct are there, and how will they be taken into account?

Question sans réponse.

Data processing and analysis

How and with what resources will the data be processed / analyzed?

Question sans réponse.

Storage and backup during the research process

How will data be stored and backed up during the research?

Data sharing and long-term preservation

How will data be shared?

Question sans réponse.

How will data be long-term preserved? Which data?

Question sans réponse.

Genetic EBV workflow using proxy data

Data description and collection or re-use of existing data

Research output description

Name	Genetic EBV workflow using proxy data
Description	<p>Co-development and validation of workflows with partners and Data Managers Development of EBV workflows for genetic data providing genetic and proxy data (WP2-WP4)</p> <p>EBV workflows could include for example (1) radio buttons for choosing one reference or simulated dataset (among many available based on conservation interests, and defined by their metadata, from WP2 or WP3), one among previously discussed sampling schemes (with Nature Managers), one Ne estimation method, (2) running the automatic resampling of a data subset, which (3) serves as input in the method, (4) finally, a conclusion is provided on the Ne accuracy (i.e. closeness to the true value), which (5) helps for deciding on best monitoring strategies.</p>
Type	Workflow
Workpackage	T5.4 - Genetic EBV workflow using proxy data
Keywords (free-text)	
Language	eng
Issued Date	
May contain personal data?	No
May contain sensible data?	No
May take ethical issues into account?	No

Will existing data be reused?

Justification Workflows can be reused for new implementation or modification

How new data will be collected or produced?

Question sans réponse.

Documentation and data quality

What metadata and documentation (for example way of organising data) will accompany the data?

Description**Use of Galaxy Platform, with four principle keys**

1. Accessibility
2. Reproducibility
3. Transparency
4. Peer review

EBV workflow steps

1. List of Necessary data and metadata to compute EBVs
2. Galaxy platform
3. Script atomization (several atomized R scripts for several input data files)
4. Script sharing (Toolshed)

Metadata language code eng

What methods will be used to ensure their scientific quality?

Question sans réponse.

Legal and ethical requirements, codes of conduct

How will other legal issues, such as intellectual property rights and ownership, be managed? What legislation is applicable?

What ethical issues and codes of conduct are there, and how will they be taken into account?

Question sans réponse.

Data processing and analysis

How and with what resources will the data be processed / analyzed?

Question sans réponse.

Storage and backup during the research process

How will data be stored and backed up during the research?

Data sharing and long-term preservation

How will data be shared?

Question sans réponse.

How will data be long-term preserved? Which data?

Question sans réponse.

Scientific report on the effects of the co-creation process

Data description and collection or re-use of existing data

Research output description

Name	Scientific report on the effects of the co-creation process
Description	We will engage stakeholders in five countries (Belgium, Denmark, France, Italy and Sweden), representing different European biogeographic regions as well as governance and management systems, in co-creating processes that include two workshops per country, complemented with short online meetings and written communication.
Type	Text
Workpackage	T6.1 - Design and facilitate co-creation processes in five countries
Language	eng
Issued Date	
May contain personal data?	No

Will existing data be reused?

Question sans réponse.

How new data will be collected or produced?

Question sans réponse.

Documentation and data quality

What metadata and documentation (for example way of organising data) will accompany the data?

Description The project aims to produce seven reports, meeting minutes, presentation slideshows, guidelines.

What methods will be used to ensure their scientific quality?

Question sans réponse.

Legal and ethical requirements, codes of conduct

How will other legal issues, such as intellectual property rights and ownership, be managed? What legislation is applicable?

Question sans réponse.

What ethical issues and codes of conduct are there, and how will they be taken into account?

Question sans réponse.

Data processing and analysis

How and with what resources will the data be processed / analyzed?

Question sans réponse.

Storage and backup during the research process

How will data be stored and backed up during the research?

Question sans réponse.

Data sharing and long-term preservation

How will data be shared?

Question sans réponse.

How will data be long-term preserved? Which data?

Question sans réponse.

Four outreach materials (StoryMaps, videos, arts, games)

Data description and collection or re-use of existing data

Research output description

Name	Four outreach materials (StoryMaps, videos, arts, games)
Description	Our social scientists will study the effects of the process on participants' knowledge, perceived usefulness of genetic indicators and willingness to implement them. Evaluate co-creation processes and outcomes. Four outreach materials (StoryMaps, videos, arts, games)
Type	Other
Workpackage	
Language	eng
Issued Date	
May contain personal data?	No

Will existing data be reused?

Question sans réponse.

How new data will be collected or produced?

Question sans réponse.

Documentation and data quality

What metadata and documentation (for example way of organising data) will accompany the data?

Description

Describe the four outreach materials (StoryMaps, videos, arts, games) + documentation

What methods will be used to ensure their scientific quality?

Question sans réponse.

Legal and ethical requirements, codes of conduct

How will other legal issues, such as intellectual property rights and ownership, be managed? What legislation is applicable?

Question sans réponse.

What ethical issues and codes of conduct are there, and how will they be taken into account?

Question sans réponse.

Data processing and analysis

How and with what resources will the data be processed / analyzed?

Question sans réponse.

Storage and backup during the research process

How will data be stored and backed up during the research?

Question sans réponse.

Data sharing and long-term preservation

How will data be shared?

Question sans réponse.

How will data be long-term preserved? Which data?

Question sans réponse.